

“CHILDREN WITH PHYSICAL DISABILITIES”

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Abstract: This article describes the causes, prevention, and treatment of children with physical disabilities. Ways of education have been revealed.

Keywords: Children, cerebral palsy, congenital defects, complex deaf- mute abnormal child, speech motor, chondrophystrophy, artogryposis, sign defect.

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Аннотация: В этой статье о детях с физическими дефектами причинах их дефектов профилактике и лечении какие виды профилактики существуют. Пути воспитания раскрыты.

Ключевые слова: Детский церебральный паралич, врожденные дефекты, комплексная глухота, немота, аномальный ребенок, речевой двигатель, хондродистрофия, артрогрипоз, дефект характера, информационная коррекция.

10% of the world’s 500 million people are disabled. Among them are also anomalous children with congenital defects. In anomalous children with congenital defects, several defects are observed together. They are called the category of anomalous children with complex defects.

Children with special needs include blind-deaf-mute children with complex disabilities. This category of children’s disability is more complex. Deaf-blind-mute children do not develop mentally due to the fact that they are deprived of the opportunity to receive information from the surrounding environment. However, thanks to specially organized support, these children have the opportunity for full intellectual development. All complex types of communication are created for them, speech is cultivated and they are perfect

From speech to speech. This allows them to complete the secondary school program and even successfully graduate from higher educational institutions. We can cite the life and work of Olga Ivanovna Skorokhodova as an example. The deaf-blind-mute girl was the famous correctional pedagogue I.A. Sokolyansky. Taught and brought up in the school-clinic he led. After graduating from the university, O. Skorokhodova spent her whole life in Correction dedicated to pedagogy.

Among children with complex physical disabilities, children with hearing impairment and mental retardation were the first to be studied. As a result, it is very difficult to distinguish between mentally healthy and hearing-impaired children from mentally retarded and hearing-impaired children. Especially in children of the first age. Currently, differential diagnostic criteria have been developed for them. The auxiliary school program in the auxiliary classes of boarding schools for children with mental development and hearing impairment receive education on Auxiliary classes are blind and partially sighted children are

also available in boarding schools Children with multiple developmental disabilities social and household adjustment

Social adjustment (adaptation) – the individual's social environment constant, active adaptation to conditions, and the result of this process. Although social adaptation occurs regularly, this process is usually from time to time in the life and activities of the individual and those around him associated with the most significant changes. The central aspect of social adaptation is the acceptance of the individual's social role. The complex rehabilitation system provides the highest possible level of training in social adaptation. It can be in three basic stages: adaptive-diagnostic, corrective and integrative, each of which performs a special task. Diagnosis of the child's personality development at the first stage is placed, and with it the possibility of rehabilitation and the most favorable correctional and educational work are determined.

In the second stage, rehabilitation activities are organized with the child is made and conducted, and the parent or guardian is rehabilitated technologies are taught. Integration of the child in the social society at the third stage ways are determined and a total complex rehabilitation is carried out within a certain period. Complex rehabilitation of a child in need of special assistance is in the following form: "medical, psychological, pedagogical and socio-economic accepted system and process, aimed at elimination, correction, or fully compensates" Its purpose is "to improve the social status, financial independence of a child in need of special assistance and rehabilitating his social adjustment".

Medical and social rehabilitation works are carried out in special educational institutions or institutions of the intemat type in the organization of the educational process for children in need of special assistance, in the process of their social and household adaptation, and in the process of identifying their specific aspects. The unique psychological characteristics of the child's personality are developed through social rehabilitation. During the process, a number of problems related to a large number of internal and external factors that arise with a child with complex multiple defects in development affect the child's development. Learning, positive and to foresee negative aspects, impact results and correction should be started on time.

Correctional work is very important in the process of working with children who need special help. The better these things are done, the easier it is for the child to acquire knowledge, skills and competences.

Specialized preschool educational institutions with different categories of children with disabilities of physical or mental development in the continuous education system under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the educational process in specialized schools and schools-intemats in the correctional direction is being implemented. Teachers, speech therapists, and educators try to implement correctional work in different ways in each lesson.

Uzbekistan's membership in the United Nations, the ratification of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, and the adoption of the Law on the Guarantees of the Rights of the Child are important for the care of our youth. Is a bright example. At the heart of all the reforms implemented in our country, first of all, the next generation will grow up to be perfect, capable of conquering the world arenas like no one else.

It is important that they grow up as children. In particular, social protection of orphans and children without parental care, disabled children, and children with complex developmental

disabilities has always been considered a priority task of the state and society. In order to fulfill this task, it is necessary to ensure the rights and freedoms and equal opportunities of people with developmental disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to eliminate restrictions and limitations in life activities, to provide education

A lot of work is being done on modern approach to organization and management, improvement of its quality and efficiency, ensuring integrity and continuity of education for different strata of the population in the society.

At the stage of childhood, a person is psychologically and pedagogically strong is affected. Corrective-pedagogical, psychological and medical work, organized taking into account the boundless internal capabilities of the growing child's body and brain structure, helps to reduce the child's primary defect and prevent secondary defects. All these are the factors of preparing the child to lead an independent, independent life.

SUMMARY.

The presence of a complex defect in a child slows down the direction of his development, reduces the possibility of correction of defects, significantly complicates the organization of the educational process. Therefore, successful work with children requires attention and a wide range of knowledge.

In schools of many integrated countries, a special management trend has been developed for students and resource centers. The role of these special schools is very important for students, the importance of these institutions brings positive results in the lives of children who need special help. But one problem is the lack of appropriate materials for children who need help. Management of the educational process in the environment in order to solve some of the following problems: special courses for children with Braille visual impairment, their parents, teachers, assistants, staff involved in the child's education or rehabilitation process. Explain to students that they need to help their visually impaired classmates to move around in the classroom.

References:

1. Mo'minova L. N. Abidova va boshqalar. Maxsus psixologiya-T O'zbekiston faylasuflar milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2013-yil
2. "Maxsus pedagogika" M.U. Xamidova Toshkent-2018
3. "Maxsus pedagogika" P.M.Po'latova, L.Sh. Nurmuxamedova, D.B.Yakubjonova, Z.N. Mamarajabova, Sh.M.Amirsaidova, A.D.Sultanova.
4. Po'latxo'jayeva M.R. Defektologiyaning klinik asoslari-T. 2012 yil
5. L.R.Mo'minova, Sh.M.Amirsaidova, Z.N. Mamarajabova, M.U.Xamidova, D.B.Yakubjanova, Z.M.Djalolova, N.Z. Abidova, Maxsus psixologiya-T. 2013 yil
6. M. Ayupova "Logopediya" 2007 yil
7. "Logopediya" (L.S. Volkova tahriri ostida) –M
8. "Logopediya" (L.Mo'minova, M. Ayupova)-T

